

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

WP2

Case 5 (GR) - Action learning Agriscapes

Case development report, cycle 3

1. ID card

1. Title, level of the course and course language

Title: Farm Animal Reproduction

Level of the course: Undergraduate, 8th semester

Course language: Greek

Host institution(s) and course leader(s)

Host institution: International Hellenic University

Course leader: Dr Aristotelis Lymberopoulos

Timeline of the activities covered in this report:

October 2020 – January 2021

Learner categories and number per category

Learner categories: Undergraduates, 2 groups

Learners: 20 total, 14 female, 6 male

Age: 18-22

2. Title, level of the course and course language

Title: Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods

Level of the course: Undergraduate

Course language: Greek

Host institution(s) and course leader(s)

Host institution: International Hellenic University

Course leader: Dr Maria Papageorgiou

Timeline of the activities covered in this report:

October 2020 – January 2021

Learner categories and number per category

Learners: 80 total, 54 female, 26 male

Age: 18-22

The activities mentioned below are part of our case report but are not reported on in detail here. They may be mentioned in our planning for next cycle activities or in some of our reflections. Please visit case 5 in the NEXTFOOD Platform for more details.

3. **Title of activity:** Installation of Precision Technology Infrastructures
Host Institution: American Farm School, SPMO department / ATEITH (TEI)
Activity leader: Dr. Philippos Papadopoulos
 - a) Installation of **digital Insect traps** in a host of affiliated farms within the North of Macedonia region.
 - b) Installation of **weather stations** within the ATEITH farm and other locations in the region of North Macedonia, recording atmosphere and soil conditions.

4. **Title of Activity:**
Collaboration with WP1: Testing of the Inventory of Skills with students in the AFS

5. **Title of activity:**
Collaboration with WP4: Workshop with policy makers and members of the Agricultural Network of Northern Greece

6. **Title of Activity:**
Collaboration with WP5: Testing of the Framework of Impact in our case

7. **Title of activity:**
Collaboration between NEXTFOOD and INoFA: Facilitation of 4 Focus groups with members of Business clusters

8. **Title of Activity:**
Seminar on the implementation of precision technologies in IHU

2. Extended summary of Development of case since the previous reporting

2.1 Actions Taken since the previous report

2.1.1 Planning

Our last report closed with the end of the spring semester of IHU academic year and the courses of Plant Protection and Animal Reproduction. During the following months we held meetings between the AFS team and with the professors to reflect on our previous year experiences and plan for the challenged we had faced during the previous cycle. One of our main aims for the next cycle was to encourage and promote more independent facilitation of action-learning on the part of the professors involved and to further enhance the multi-actor approach with more extra-organizational activities and stakeholder involvement. We also spent time networking and finding external stakeholders that were willing to participate in the project and the next cycle activities. Unfortunately, there was considerable ambiguity as to the format that the present cycle courses/activities would have due to the emerging pandemic. Thus, our planning had to include an adaptation of the curricula to accommodate for on-line action-learning and also the training of our professors for this type of teaching while maintaining the action-learning principles and the multi-stakeholder approach. The outcome of our planning was that by the beginning of our two courses everyone was fully prepared for both the live-teaching and the on-line scenarios and there were multiple events planned with extra-organizational actors to participate in the sessions.

2.1.2 Implementation

The implementation had to be on-line for the entirety of the academic year, due to government restrictions. The sessions for both courses were organized in a way that included lecturing, student participation, peer-to-peer learning, a diversity of learning sources and reflection. Due to the nature of on-line learning, the above elements were more restricted than the past learning cycle and were done in a more “artificial” and formally organized manner. In order to enhance the multi-actor approach, there were two virtual visits organized for each module. Unfortunately, time restrictions were magnified in the on-line environment and we could not include all the visits we would like.

We anticipated that teachers might have limited interaction with the students and that students would react to reflection activities as something unnecessary, time consuming and boring. We tried to overcome these difficulties by being actively present throughout the activities and by offering our support and guidance whenever needed. In the beginning of the module, we had presentations on major reflection theories, on how to do effective reflection. Based on our past

cycle experiences we also expected a considerable knowledge and skill gap in research methodology, We covered this gap by dedicating two sessions on how to perform literature searches, evaluate resources, write essays and do successful oral presentations.

The professors we were working with had already gone through the experience of action-based module implementation and responded well to our suggestion and implementation strategies.

On the whole the implementation of the modules went smoothly and without major practical challenges, except for the overall challenging factors that were out of our control.

2.1.3 Reflection

Teacher reflections were done informally after almost each on-line session. Together with the professors we reflected on how they thought the session went, if we needed to do any adjustments and how we would proceed in the next session. The professors were asked to do one formal written reflection at the end of the module.

2.2 Research results since the previous reporting

2.2.1 Students', teachers' and other stakeholders's experiences and learning

The students that took part in the modules mostly reported positively on their experiences. Of course, their positive experience was relative to other “traditional” learning modules since they very often commented on how the on-line environment was very restricting and not suited for practical studies such as animal reproduction. However, the most prevalent features of the module that were reported on were the multi-actor approach with the virtual visits, the support with their research projects, the team-projects and student presentations and the photo-novella project.

The stakeholders' experiences were also regarded positive. They participated enthusiastically and mentioned that such collaborations should take place more often. They were very willing to discuss with students, answer questions and share important aspects of their work and vision. However, learning was linear with them taking the role of instructor in most cases.

Based on our observations and group reflections, facilitators experiences this learning cycle with mixed feelings but did show a very good level of adaptability and competence with regards to the pandemic circumstances. As with students, professors viewed on-line teaching as very limiting in all respects. However, they did show greater levels of independence regarding action-learning and they reported high levels of satisfaction about attempting the NEXTFOOD shifts both regarding their job as educators and with regards to their students' experience.

2.2.2 Outcome of the case development process, including effects of making the essential shifts

Despite the pandemic conditions, the Greek case developed its activities for the best possible outcomes. These conditions had a twofold effect on our case activities as a whole. First, new possibilities were offered for connections that would be very difficult before, due to time and distance restrictions. Since everyone became familiarized with on-line meetings we were able to conduct numerous workshops with different stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, which we would not have done otherwise. This had a positive effect both for our students and for our project processes as a whole. On the same note, all our actors and stakeholders had the opportunity to develop new competences and explore on-line possibilities, many of which will remain in their toolbox long after the pandemic has ended.

On the other side, students were deprived of very important opportunities for hands-on and socially and sensory rich experiences. This inevitably affected the shifts of the NextFOOD Project adversely because the medium through which we attempted them could never substitute live contact.

Having said that, the reported outcomes of actor experiences show evidence of a very positive effect in all activities but we must take into account that mostly students reported in numerous occasions that on-line learning is very limiting. With regard to professional actors that we worked with, we observed that, because communication became more easy and effortless in digital environments the NEXTFood Project shifts became more widely disseminated and connections and collaborations became easier.

2.2.3 Supporting and Hindering forces for implementing the NEXTFood model.

The hindering forces for change towards the NEXTFOOD approach that we continuously come across in our work is the lack of competence related culture within the universities, a general lack of a concrete conceptual framework for sustainability and the lack of experience with action-learning. These are issues that we have tackled directly with the professors and students that we have been working with.

In addition, we came across a few cases where students were not willing to work with us, saw our work as unnecessary and irrelevant and thought that traditional teaching was more suitable. These instances have shown us that even though it is widely accepted that action-learning has numerous academic benefits, the shifts to a sustainable future need to be reached in a flexible manner and that we need to accept that the goal of sustainable development may be more important than the means by which we try to achieve it.

Hindering forces on a higher level, as we have seen during numerous workshops and focus groups that we have carried out during this and previous working cycles are the general lack of connection between academia and other actors in society who would be able to inform and update curricula and offer opportunities for experiential learning.

On the other hand, there are numerous supporting forces as we have observed in the classes and as we have seen in our focus groups, reflection logs and based on our experience with student workshops. These are based on the very high motivational level of the actors we have worked with so far. There seems to be a great need from the part of students to participate in multi-actor, action-based activities and they are very receptive to ideas concerning sustainability. It seems that it is increasingly becoming a part of everyday social narratives and thus, younger generations may be more sensitive to and accepting of innovative ideas that support it. Professors on the other hand, are dealing with a great deal of professional stressors like time limitation, budget limitations, and organizational hazards. However, action-learning seems to improve their relationship with their students and this allows for greater job satisfaction. Finally, professional actors and organizations have shown to have a high level of interest in connecting with Universities in order to fill skill gaps in their fields and to interconnect with the other parts of the system (political as well as academic).

3. Data on the development of case since the previous reporting

3.1 Students' responses, learning and competence development

3.1.1 Methods of data collection and analysis

Following the structure suggested by D 2.1 (Action Research Protocol) the data collection procedures followed four stages (Stage 1, 2, 3).

Stage 1 took place during the **first week of the modules**. The students' understanding and expectations of the course were the main aim of the Stage 1. Following D 2.1 (Action Research Protocol) students were provided with a set of open-ended questions that were completed individually by all course participants on-line.

During the first day of the educational activity students also completed the **"Self-assessment of competences"** questionnaire aiming to assess their knowledge and abilities and to depict their competence profile in the following areas: observation, participation, visioning, reflection and dialogue.

Stage 2 took place during the **last week of the modules**. Following D 2.1 (Action Research Protocol) students were provided with the same set of open-ended questions (**Student Reflection Documents**) that were completed individually by all course participants on-line.

During the last day of educational activities the students also completed for the “**Self-assessment of competences**” questionnaire for a second time. The completion of the “Self-assessment of competences” aimed at identifying differences in the perceptions of the students by comparing the results of the questionnaire at the beginning and at the end of the course.

Stage 3 of the data collection took place after the completion of the modules. **8 Focus groups** with the students that attended the courses took place. Students formed 6 groups (4-6 participants per group) and participated in group interviews aiming to discuss the experience they gained from their participation in the course. The group interviews lasted from 1-1.5 hours. The researchers acted as facilitators of the discussion that evolved around the five competences.

A written consent for the participation of the students in all research activities was asked at the beginning of the course. All students read and signed the consent forms. The group interviews were audio recorded and transcribed into Greek. Selected quotations that used for supporting argumentation for the coding adopted were translated into English.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis, one of the most commonly used forms for the analysis of qualitative research, was used to identify codes, subcodes and family of codes and to analyse and interpret common patterns and themes within the qualitative data. (Boyatzis, 1998; Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Qualitative data analysis was assisted by the ATLAS.ti software as it was used to organise the text (interviews), facilitated the activities of searching and retrieving, selecting, organising and comparing segments of data. Quantitative data analysis of the data of the “Self-assessment of competences” questionnaire was assisted by the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.1.1.1 Student understanding, contributions and expectations.

During the first week of sessions, the NEXTFood Project, the educational model and its thematic relativity to their studies was introduced to the students. By doing this, we attempted to ensure that all students had a firm understanding of the educational model we would be working in, the competences we were aiming to enhance and why competence development was important to their education. Building on our previous experience, we also aimed to establish understanding of what is meant by “sustainability” and “sustainable development”. We attempted this by way of instruction and open conversation in order to promote questions and dialogue.

After these introductions, students were sent the first reflection documents, in digital form, to report their understanding, expectations and how they anticipate contributing to the aims of the module. The questions were open ended and allowed for individual elaboration. The answers were collected and coded based on the competence tree provided by the research protocol using the Atlas qualitative analysis software.

3.1.1.2 Self-assessment of competences

During the first and the final week of the course students completed the self-assessment of the competences questionnaire to identify development of their core competences. Students were asked to rank their level of competence on several items using a scale from 1 (Novice) – 9 (Expert). Students who participated in both courses completed the questionnaire.

3.1.1.3 Students' final reflection document (Individual)

The students' final reflection documents as presented in the research protocol document were sent and collected in digital form in the final week of the course. To ensure that students would all fill in the reflection documents, they were given 20 minutes of the class session in order to complete them. The completion was compulsory.

3.1.2 Results

Tables 1 and 2 present a comparison of the means from the first and the final week of the courses. Comparisons of the means indicate differences in the competences identified by the self-assessment rubric.

A paired-samples t-test was conducted to compare between the two sets of the questionnaire. As shown in Tables 1 and 2 students ranked their competence development higher in both courses. In the "Farm Animal Reproduction" course students indicated higher mastery in the participation, visioning, reflection and dialogue competence. In the "Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods" course the largest increase was in participation and observation. In the "Farm Animal Reproduction" course the largest increase was in participation, reflection and visioning. The largest increase in the "Farm Animal Reproduction" course was identified in the participation and reflection competences, which may be due to students' involvement to the group project and presentation and to their engagement to the reflection activities.

On the other hand, students of the course "Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods" started ranking quite high all indicated competences. They seem to overestimate their competences. Such overestimation may be explained by the fact that they are first semester students who do not have the academic experience needed to appreciate the development of necessary skills and abilities.

Table 1: Average scores of self-reported competence development for the course “Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods”. The scale used was 1 (Novice) – 9 (Expert). N=80.

Competences	Average scores			Significance
	Start	End	Diff	P value ¹
Observation	4,75	5,74	+0,99	<.0001***
Participation	5,37	6,34	+0,97	<.0001***
Visioning	5,47	6,02	+0,55	<.0001***
Reflection	5,40	6,19	+0,79	<.0001***
Dialogue	6,24	6,87	+0,63	<.0001***

*: p-value < .05, **: p-value < .01, ***: p-value < .001

Table 2: Average scores of self-reported competence development for the course “Farm Animal Reproduction”. The scale used was 1 (Novice) – 9 (Expert). N=21.

Competences	Average scores			Significance
	Start	End	Diff	P value ¹
Observation	3,52	4,39	+0,87	<.0001***
Participation	4,09	6,19	+2,10	<.0001***
Visioning	4,22	5,61	+1,39	<.0001***
Reflection	4,53	6,41	+1,88	<.0001***
Dialogue	5,35	6,53	+1,18	<.0001***

*: p-value < .05, **: p-value < .01, ***: p-value < .001

With regards to the reflection documents, we observe a difference between the starting and end reflection documents. The first week reflections were considerably shorter and less elaborate than the final ones. They showed awkwardness in the process of reflection and a lack

of reflective competence. Evidence of this is that answers were mostly very short and repeated the terminology that we used in the introductory class. In addition, when asked of the expectations students had of the course they mostly repeated the knowledge content of the course and expressed that they be educated in these issues.

The end reflection documents reflect a development in the competence of reflection, although some awkwardness was still present. Students by large found it difficult to answer questions of process (“how” questions). However, we observe better understanding of what was expected from them and attempt to explain in more detail and depth their experience.

3.1.2.1 How do students experience such a learning process with respect to:

3.1.2.1.1 Learning goals?

At the beginning of each module we dedicated half a session in order to discuss with the students the learning outcomes of the module. During the discussions, we saw that students were generally not used to being part of such discussions and viewed their participation as a passive process of knowledge transference from the professor to the student. The learning outcomes that they expected were largely content based and even so, they had a very vague and general idea of what they were going to be taught. Their concerns evolved largely around practical questions about subject choices and how the module would be delivered and assessed and what this meant for their general studies. During this first session, we tried to engage students into a general conversation about the six core competences, sustainable development and what it meant for someone to be part of the agricultural chain as a student. The idea of competence development seemed entirely novel to them, although it was positively accepted. The general participation in the conversation was low but the students that chose to participate in the conversation showed curiosity and positivity. The low participation could also be due to the fact that the conversation was on-line and we have seen that many students felt intimidated to open their microphones and speak. We explained that part of the learning outcomes of the modules would be to develop these competences and we took time to explain each competence in detail.

As the sessions progressed, students engaged more in the learning process and felt more in control of their learning. The feeling that we got from our class observations and by student performance was that students owned the responsibility of their learning to greater extent. Having said that, we still observed low class participation during the lecture sessions and the facilitator had to insist on engagement in the discussions with questions that were addressed to specific students, because they seldom opened their microphones spontaneously. On average, only about 10% of students participated actively in each session. We observed higher

participation in the Animal Reproduction module. The number of students in this module was lower and they were at a higher level in their studies than the Nutrition module.

With regards to the student perception of the learning process, students often refer to the factor of “will” in a number ways in their reflections. For example they refer to the fact that certain aspects of the classes increased their will to participate or that “will” is an important factor in the way that projects turn out. From this we may start inferring the motivational strength of action-learning methodologies.

Reflecting on the experience they have gained through the class a student of the animal reproduction module says:

“Surely, we look at things in a more mature way. We recognise what is good and not in the field of reproduction of farm animals” Student Reflection Documents (SRD) 63:9

Another observation was that a large number of students, especially in the animal reproduction module, mention that their learning was hindered significantly by the on-line learning environment, because it deprived them of the practical experience they needed from the face to face lab sessions. This is completely understandable, since it is a highly practical module that needs hands-on experience in order to reach the learning goals of the module.

Students stressed the value of participation and how the present situation has affected this competence:

“The part of experiential and practical training remains incomplete” SRD 63:15

But they also mention that the module, while on-line helped them to remain connected to the subject in a meaningful way:

“It is very important to stay in contact with the subject since, due to the circumstances we have become distanced from our university and from the field of our future profession” SRD 63:17

3.1.2.1.2 View on competences needed for sustainable development?

As mentioned before, students generally began the courses with a very vague idea, of what sustainable development means. From previous learning cycles and interviews in the course of the NEXTFOOD PROJECT we have seen that neither students nor professors have a firm grasp on ideas of sustainability or what is needed to follow sustainable development. Also, the idea of skills and competences itself is difficult to incorporate in their view of their education. However, we saw that after the discussions we had, students began to think about this matter in a promising way.

From the student reflections we see that students tend to talk about attitudes in the same way as they talk about competences. Here, we come across a challenge of methodology and definition in our work which is quite predictable. We need to accept that sustainable development relies on changes in attitudes as well as the development of competences. That is, we need to view and investigate our educational activities as an amalgamation of transformative learning in both attitudinal and competence terms. As such, we accept and incorporate a number of comments on attitudes as well as competences that students perceive as important for sustainable development.

Students tended to remain constant in the importance they place on acquisition of hard skills and content knowledge. The majority of students answered this question by referring to specific knowledge they think is important in their field. They mostly referred to specific aspects of Farm Animal reproduction and Nutritional values of food groups. One student framed this as knowledge being the basis on which they could build their competences:

“From this module I gained more and more detailed knowledge on which I can base my competences in order to support sustainable development in the field of Nutrition” SRD 63:86

However, showing a growing awareness of their field development students also reflect on skills, competences and personal traits that they find important:

- Research skills
- Respect toward the environment and its resources. They also often refer to the will to continue developing and educating oneself as highly important.
«Some basic skills are respect to the environment and to make the best possible use of the resources that it offers us” SRD 63:19

and

“the will for continuous development on our field and continuous education” SRD 63:10

- Knowledge on technological advancements. They mention the need for updated knowledge about technological advancements and continued education:
“I believe that it is vital to be informed not only in nutritional subjects but also in technology so that our skills and knowledge keep in pace with the advances of society” SRD 63:64
- The need for increased willingness, participation, for critical thinking and for assuming personal responsibility.
- The need for ethical development in sustainability issues
- Logical thinking, creative thinking and intuitive thinking.
- Innovation

- Team work, a holistic view and understanding of the role of nutrition for a sustainable future.

E.g

“The skills that someone needs are, collectivity, the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking. For these to develop there is a need to learn from our training as a whole and from our practical training” SRD 63:100

“ For a start I believe that everyone who is involved in the field of nutrition needs to have an holistic view of things. They need to be informed in all fields: physical, spiritual and psychological” SRD 63:75

- Knowledge of the aims and objectives of sustainable development so that a person can develop innovative ideas.
- The need for a change in attitude toward sustainability rather than market value driven food quality; higher sense of responsibility by stakeholders.
- Knowledge on the environmental footprint of food products

In closing,

“For supporting sustainable development in the field of Nutrition, it is most important to have a stance of solidarity, respect for human rights and trust and support to innovative ideas” SRD 63:88

Specific attitudes that were inferred by the student responses to this question were, proactivity, openness, willingness, love for the subject, patience, reconciliatory attitude and objectivity. Solidarity and respect were also mentioned as attitudes that may support sustainable development. The will to learn and develop seems to re occur very often in student comments.

3.1.2.1.3 Recognition of own competences and competence development?

Students were called to recognize their own competence development through the reflection on how they contributed to the learning experience of the activities. They were asked about the competences that they brought to the experience and they also reflected on how the activities helped them develop their competences. Based on their reflections’ responses students found most important and developed

- Social skills through the group projects. Specifically they commented on developing patience, cooperation and organizational skills.
- Prominent in student comments are research skills, with numerous comments on how they learned to search for trustworthy sources, the ability to discriminate between relevant and good quality information (critical thinking) and the ability to put together documents that are scientifically valid.

- The ability to combine knowledge from different aspects of their fields and to transfer theoretical knowledge to real life situations
- Presentation skills
- Dialogue, communication skills, expression of ideas, listening and understanding others
 - “I was able to connect better with the members of my team and to share with them relevant knowledge, ideas and experiences in order to contribute to their learning experience” SRD 63:121

and

“I could contribute to my team by forming conditions and questions that fostered dialogue and cooperation and also by appreciating the opinions of all my teammates. By doing this I could collect and evaluate them with the aim of creating a final stance that all the team could support” SRD 63:112

- Reflection
- Observation
- Participation
- Critical thinking
- Facilitation
 - “The work of the professors and my work as a student and our good cooperation contributed to the very positive development of the class” SRD 63:124
- manifold thinking
 - «(...)my ability to look at the subject from all the possible angles so that we could cover it all the possible implications that were related to it” SRD 63:130
- Technological competences
- Visionary thinking/insight
- Leadership skills
- Goal setting and achievement of goals
- Attentiveness
- Creative thinking

Here we will also mention some of the attitudes that students perceived as important from their part in the learning experience and the attitudes that the activities helped them develop. For example they often mentioned

- Respectfulness
- Sociability/extraversion
- Optimism
- Self-confidence
- Stamina
- Willingness
- Commitment
- Self-confidence

- Diligence
- Openness to diverse information and mindsets (a crucial attitude for transformative learning)
- Patience

3.1.2.1.4 Transformation?

Students refer to how the activities and the learning experiences from the modules transformed them in many different ways and in many different occasions.

Transformation occurred in frames of mind, their view of the field standards, their personal emotional and mental development and their willingness to participate and take responsibility in their field. These reflections took place by large with reference to the issue of food loss/food waste, after the virtual visit by a non-profit food waste organization. Some good examples of transformative learning are:

“Personally, I reconsidered my actions on issues of sustainability and I understood that we need a different model of living that aims at the best possible environmental outcome. In this way the quality of life will improve for people and at the same time their ability to cover their future needs and expectations will be strengthened.” SRD 63:139

“I have understood a little bit more about reality; I reconsidered some things that I took for granted and from now on I will try to contribute as much as possible to the elimination or the reduction of several every-day problems in the field of nutrition” SRD 63:141

“ (...)I have questions now regarding the improvement of different issues. E.g. land that is not used for cultivation, over-consumption, wrong use of best-before-dates etc”. SRD 63:140

“I can understand now that many of the food products that we consume daily are not as they are presented to the public and that ignorance for what is within those products can lead to a lower quality in life and even to disease” SRD 63:135

In the Animal Reproduction module many students reflected on the emotional impact of the group project. A good example was:

“ I became able to say my opinion when it was needed. That is...even if I had an opposite opinion in some issues (something that I found difficult in the beginning); because I wanted the project to be good, without imperfections and because we all had

responsibility for the project, I didn't want to be exposed with mistakes. I also took initiative and helped other when they needed it" SRD 63:41

3.1.2.2 To what extent does the education enhance the students'

3.1.2.2.1 Competence of observation, reflection, visionary thinking, participation, dialogue?

As mentioned before, the educational activities have played a significant role in the development and enhancement of the six core competences. Most of our activities involved a mixture of competence development with some targeting competences in more direct ways than others.

For example we included the lectures on reflection. This activity was designed to introduce the competence of reflection in a more concrete way. By this activity we aimed to introduce a cognitive framework that would help students practice reflection more fluently and more precisely. Thus, this activity increased the cognitive capacity for the competence of reflection directly. We also aimed at engaging in oral, group reflection for a few minutes after each class. Additionally, we included an extra activity-reflection-log for the groups that were involved in the Photo Novella Projects apart from the initial and ending formal on-line reflections that were done by all students. During all these activities, all the other competences were enhanced in a theoretical and cognitive way.

This cycle's activities had certain specificities that may have hindered the optimal enhancement of observation, participation and dialogue. The on-line environment, added to the general uncertainty and novelty of the academic proceedings may have played a negative role in students' learning experience and may have hindered the competence development of less technologically or introverted individuals. However, with the activities we designed, we went at great lengths to ensure the best possible outcomes of a very negative scenario. Here, we would like to make a special reference to one of our activities, which was added to one of the modules, experimentally. It was the Photo Novella Project, taken by half of the students in the Nutrition Module and which targets all the core competences in a creative and participatory way. Students were divided into groups and were asked to choose between a variety of subjects on Nutrition and develop a photographic gallery of photographic representations on the subject, while linking it to sustainability. They were also asked to keep a reflection diary while on the project and to present their gallery to invoke conversation with their peers. The reflection documents from this activity produced a very rich variety of responses with regards to the core competences and more specifically on observation and participation:

On urban farming:

“The image of a bird sitting on a tree branch helped me understand that we could find anything we wanted, anywhere. (...) for a bird or animal it is not strange to find food in an urban environment. On the contrary, we humans find it very strange to see a crop in the city and this might be something that we need to change” Photo Novella Diary Reflections (PNDR)19:2

and

“The photographs of my project are quite realistic and so my feelings are mostly admiration, satisfaction, fantasy and optimism when I think of how my city could look like if we used the available land for farming” PNDR 26:1

On genetically modified foods:

“This image might be frightening but at the same time it makes us think and it creates a sort of curiosity regarding the genetic modification of foods” PNDR 20:2

and

«Are scientists genuinely interested in the quality of foods that are offered to consumers or is profit the only aim?” PNDR 20:3

The same student later considers a different perspective...

«With the cultivation of genetically modified food there is considerable limitation of pesticides and fertilizers in the crops. With this way, there is better waste processing and management, so the environment is better protected. Nature “breathes” better” PNDR 20:4

And general reflections on the process:

“Taking pictures and doing research gave me a different point of view for the food we consume. My feelings about the images are mixed since, as you will see, they incline the viewer that they are negative but they hide positive sides as well.” PNDR 54:2

and

“Exchanging photographs with my group contributed to me learning about the nutritional habits of two families, which was very interesting” PNDR 51:3

From the above and other such reflections, we concluded that this was a successful activity for enhancing all core competences.

Other than this activity, the responses that we received from the students, contribute to our understanding that the most impactful activities for competence development are the group projects, the involvement of professional field actors in the modules and the training in research methods.

3.1.2.2.1 Dealing with “the challenge of the whole” (systems thinking)

It seems that most of our activities have contributed significantly to students' awareness of the agricultural and food systems as a whole. They became more able to appreciate different perspectives, to appreciate the complexity of the systems involved and to see themselves as part of these systems with a sense of responsibility and agency.

Having said that, this cycle's activities, under the pandemic circumstances gave us no opportunity to observe students' ability to deal with this complexity and to become problem solvers within these systems in a practical and concrete manner. To a limited degree, students had the opportunity to discuss real life problems and difficulties with the professional actors and the facilitators. However, the circumstances did not allow for hands-on experience.

3.2 Teachers' and other stakeholders' perceptions of the overall process of developing the case towards the NEXTFood approach in education

3.2.1 Methods of data collection and analysis

3.2.1.1 Teacher reflection documents

The facilitators of our modules, Dr. Aristotelis Lymberopoulos and Dr. Maria Papageorgiou prepared reflection documents providing feedback and a description of their involvement, the perceived development of students' competences, main themes and issues and a plan for further improvement of the courses “Farm Animal Reproduction” and “Nutritional Value of Foods”. These documents were collected, coded in Atlas and analysed using thematic analysis.

3.2.1.2 Course reflection focus groups

8 Focus groups with the students that attended the courses took place. Students formed 6 groups (4-6 participants per group) and participated in group interviews aiming to discuss the experience they gained from their participation in the course. The group interviews lasted from

1-1.5 hours. The researchers acted as facilitators of the discussion that evolved around the five competences.

3.2.2 Results

The reflection documents of the facilitators and the student focus groups offer as considerable insight into the effect of the NEXTFood approach on the perceptions of the actors involved in action-learning. As mentioned before, the facilitators have gained a variety of benefits regarding their satisfaction as educators and their perception of student satisfaction and competence. On the whole, facilitators reported motivation to continue with the action-learning model and that they experienced a shift in their educator mind-set. They also gained insight of the role of real economy actors in the formation of their module curricula and more experience in their communication with real economy actors. They perceive these experiences as valuable and an asset to their personal development.

On the other hand, it was pointed out that since the COVID-19 pandemic had affected the educational system, they had to move their educational activities online and this had a perceived negative impact on his and his students' learning experience.

Dr. Lymperopoulos commented that students benefited by their participation in the group projects and that the group working approach added to the students' learning experience as they have the opportunity to manage their time more effectively, to work with peers, to know each other better, to better understand their topics. Additionally, students who demonstrated proficiency in a skill can bring their expertise and experience to the group and the group can benefit from that.

Furthermore, students had the opportunity to participate in online live sessions with sector stakeholders who presented their farms and took part in fruitful discussions about farm management.

As it was pointed out by Dr Lymberopoulos:

"(...) we wanted to encourage active learning and provide an opportunity for the development of key skills such as communication, group working and problem solving".

Later in his reflection he comments that the main aim of redesigning the course was the acquisition of skills important in the farming industry:

"With this we tried to provide young students with the right attitude, an appreciation of the importance of the sector, farming knowledge, skills and science in the practice of farming industry".

Students on the other hand reported very positively on the experience of these modules, as is evident from the analysis in the previous sections. The focus groups, perhaps more than the written reflection documents, reflect a development in the core competences and an awareness of the complexity of real life circumstances. Most students during the focus groups showed high willingness to participate, engage and contribute to the discussion in a productive and creative way.

There were also instances of indifference, lack of motivation and a general sense that the activities were an obligation to be delivered. This is understandable in the sense that many students were not in the course of choice in the first place and also there are considerable and expected differences in personality, attitudes and learning styles within any given educational environment.

3.2.2.1 Supporting and Hindering forces for change towards the NEXTFood approach with particular focus on essential shifts

The hindering forces for change towards the NEXTFOOD approach that we continuously come across in our work is the lack of competence related culture within the universities, a general lack of a concrete conceptual framework for sustainability and the lack of experience with action-learning. These are issues that we have tackled directly with the professors and students that we have been working with. However, we are very aware that we are working with a very small number of people within a very large educational system.

Hindering forces on a higher level, as we have seen during numerous workshops and focus groups that we have carried out during this and previous working cycles are the general lack of connection between academia and other actors in society who would be able to inform and update curricula and offer opportunities for experiential learning.

On the other hand, there are numerous supporting forces as we have observed in the classes and as we have seen in our focus groups, reflection logs and based on our experience with student workshops. These are based on the very high motivational level of the actors we have worked with so far. There seems to be a great need from the part of students to participate in multi-actor, action-based activities and they are very receptive to ideas concerning sustainability. It seems that it is increasingly becoming a part of everyday social narratives and thus, younger generations may be more sensitive to and accepting of innovative ideas that support it. Professors on the other hand, are dealing with a great deal of professional stressors like time limitation, budget limitations, and organizational hazards. However, action-learning seems to improve their relationship with their students and this allows for greater job satisfaction. Finally, professional actors and organizations have shown to have a high level of interest in connecting with Universities in order to fill skill gaps in their fields and to interconnect with the other parts of the system (political as well as academic).

3.2.2.1.1 From lecture hall to a diversity of learning arenas

The course "Farm Animal Reproduction" consisted of lectures, classroom activities and exercises. Due to COVID-19 pandemic and the government restrictions for higher education the course was delivered on-line. The module curriculum was delivered mainly through on-line lectures with the exception of a few lab sessions in the beginning of the module. Under these circumstances, the AFS together with the module facilitator, went to great lengths to re-design and accommodate the delivery methodology in line with international on-line action-based best-practices. The students were involved in synchronous and asynchronous action-based learning activities aiming at their active involvement and engagement in the educational processes. Our central concern was the connection of theoretical background with real-life

farming practices and we used case-studies, exercises and discussions with the teacher and sector stakeholders. They also participated in 2 live-connection sessions with farmers. One, related to the lab practice of sperm collection and the other related to new technologies in milk production farming and estrus synchronization.

The course “Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods” module also consisted of lectures, classroom activities and exercises. This module was also delivered on-line due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions. Students investigated the theoretical knowledge gained through lectures through two group action-based learning activities. Half of the groups performed a literature review and made an oral online presentation. The other half of the groups were involved in a participatory research project based on the Photo novella methodology. They chose a subject and were called to create a personal photograph presentation to their classmates. Reflection was an integral part of the activities. We also included sector stakeholder live-connection visits that covered the topics of food loss and food waste and the connection of traditional cooking ingredients and practices with new knowledge, practices and ingredients.

Students did not initially anticipate the relevance and the help offered by such presentations. However, we were pleasantly surprised by how students embraced all activities. This was depicted in their reflection documents.

Our team, both from the AFS and IHU, learned valuable lessons on how to effectively communicate online and we also need to lean more on how to facilitate student engagement.

3.2.2.1.1.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

One of the greatest supporting forces of this year’s cycle was the lessons learnt during this cycle was the fact the classroom can go anywhere using digital tools. Facilitators and students became very experienced in the use of technology which means that in the future they may use these competences to involve much more extra-institutional activity in their classrooms.

3.2.2.1.1.2 Hindering forces and how to deal with them

The problems that remain regarding a diversification of learning arenas are those of individual motivation and participation.

Although these are not easily dealt with in a fixed manner, building an academic culture of participation and active involvement may serve as motivation for practices that involve alternative teaching arenas.

3.2.2.1.2 From lecturing to co- and peer learning

Both courses were designed around peer learning activities via engaging in group projects. In the "Farm Animal Reproduction" course the student groups engaged in literature searches and reviews on topics suggested by the facilitator. The activity ended with oral presentations of the group essays during the online class. In the course “Nutrition and Nutritional Value of Foods”

module peer learning took place via group projects (literature review and Photo Novella projects). Here too, all student group projects concluded with on-line class presentations.

3.2.2.1.2.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

One of the main supporting factors is the fact that team projects and peer learning are a major time management tool in large classes. This serves as motivation for the facilitator.

Other than that, peer learning has proven to be a valuable tool for the introduction of a variety of resources that would remain untapped if only one person was responsible (facilitator). It also gives opportunities for creative and critical thinking. These are all valuable teaching tools that can be brought forward with just one activity. This is both time and resource efficient as a teaching methodology.

3.2.2.1.2.2 Hindering forces and how to deal with them

The potential obstacles that we anticipated were the students' limited experience in using participatory knowledge construction techniques and also time limitations, since participatory techniques usually have a very high time demand. The online delivery of the course worsened the team management procedures. The students' reflections also demonstrated and identified the need for more effective team management skills.

These obstacles were overcome by careful planning and structured implementation of the activities. Clear instructions and support were provided to our students along the way by breaking the group project activities into smaller pieces and by providing guidance through related online lectures. Additionally, the students had to address issues relating to online group dynamics development and this was initially thought of as an obstacle to the successful completion of the activities. Evidence from the focus group discussions suggested that students struggled with the online group interactions as they demanded organization skills and time management skills. Student motivation and commitment to the group tasks differed among group participants. However, students commented that group sensibilities and competences were developed further due to the interaction with the online group. Valuable lessons such as time-management, group structuring and support and student management. Focus group discussions and reflection documents suggest that students can re-use the experience gained through online group interactions and further develop their skills as their online learning experience continues to grow.

It became evident that as a research team we need to promote better student group learning and to provide training in the development of online group dynamics by suggesting related methods, mechanisms and strategies for handling online group interactions such as online group leadership, conflict resolution and facilitation of online group decision-making procedures.

3.2.2.1.3 From syllabus to supporting literature / diversity of learning sources

The diversity of learning sources was a central concern in designing both modules that participated in the case. In the both modules a variety of learning sources including both internal (cognitive) and external were used to enhance students' learning and to facilitate learning activities (training in the use of major scientific databases like PubMed, Scopus, google scholar, research techniques for information searching, presentation of criteria for web pages' evaluation. Our previous experience was that students had limited skills in this domain and we aimed to promote the student's use of various resources as well as their critical thinking and source evaluation skills. We included literature searches as action-based learning activities in both modules for the completion of group projects.

During this cycle we also decided to experiment with a different, more experiential, aesthetic and emotive learning source. That is, during the Photo Novella Project, students were called to include their personal imagination, their creative thinking, their emotional capacities and their environment as a source of learning. This turned out to be a very effective method, since it produced rich reflections and a very high occurrence of transformative learning experiences, observations and visionary thinking.

3.2.2.1.3.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

Both teachers and students responded positively to the incorporation of different learning resources into the syllabi, although it may be difficult to leave the security of the textbook. The positive response is a major supporting force.

Guidance into all aspects of a literature search made students more confident and helped them engage in such activities. It is highly important to our students' future development and the development of our case that we emphasize on this and continue to train our students to use alternative and diverse methods of learning.

3.2.2.1.3.2 Hindering forces and how to deal with them

The lack of previous experience and skills on the part of students and professors is the major hindering force. So, in students the feelings of insecurity and uncertainty about the quality of their work and knowledge may be the most prevalent challenges of these activities. During the presentations, we observed many instances of this insecurity. Here again, training and the opportunity to test new sources with the relevant support may be the best way to deal with these challenges.

3.2.2.1.4 From textbook to a diversity of teaching aids

The students were introduced, trained and used a variety of action learning and teaching techniques aiming to mark the transition from textbook to a diversity of teaching techniques.

3.2.2.1.4.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

The on-line classroom environment offered a major opportunity for utilizing on-line teaching resources. For example, in the Nutrition module we made use of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations web page and applications for the curriculum purposes. Students were encouraged to use relevant applications for keeping a nutritional diary and to investigate production practices, food labeling and consumer behavior practices based on information from the FAO resources. The same occurred in the Animal Reproduction module, where it became standard practice to use on-line videos and professional farmer sites as teaching aid and case studies. Before the beginning of the modules, when we were preparing for the possibility of on-line teaching, we had extensive meetings with both facilitators in order to investigate on-line teaching resources, practices and methodologies. This preparation turned out to be valuable and opened possibilities for the facilitators that may become permanent teaching aids.

Reflection is an important teaching aid and it is much appreciated as a method of translating experience into learning because students have the opportunity to think about their experience, analyze it, evaluate it and eventually learn from it. Most activities were accompanied by self and group reflections. During the online sessions students were either provided with one question for a brief reflection or they took part in group discussion and reflection. To facilitate group reflection in the online environment students were split in breakout rooms.

Finally, most of the online course activities were accompanied by discussion, one of the most effective and interactive methods for strengthening learning. Students were encouraged by the facilitators to share their ideas on topics under discussion and present their views. However, since discussion is a useful teaching technique that is appreciated and used extensively, teachers need to receive additional training on facilitating online discussions.

Here again, the motivation and willingness of all parties involved, to learn and adapt to the circumstances was the most important factor of the success. Maintaining this momentum and this motivation is key to the shift.

3.2.2.1.4.2 Hinderling forces and how to deal with them

As before, lack of familiarity, lack of confidence and skill gaps, are the major challenges both for students and professors. Again, training, giving opportunities for alternative teaching aids and promoting examples of such practices are important ways to deal with these challenges.

3.2.2.1.5 From written exam to a diversity of assessment methods

Both courses incorporated both direct and indirect methods of assessment in measuring the student's learning outcomes. Direct methods mainly aimed to check students' learning against specific standards, while indirect methods aimed to engage students to reflect on their experiences, therefore, learning. A combination of direct and indirect assessment methods were used in both modules.

Written exams, group project literature review, group project presentation, reflection activities were the main assessment methods that were used to assess the students' learning outcomes. Indirect activities were linked with a grade. Students were given a percentage of the final mark (20%) for filling in reflections and for participating in the group activities and discussions. Additionally, activities included embedded assessments. For example, the group project mark assessed the group's performance for the production of the literature review but also assessed the students' ability to locate scientific information and journal articles and to evaluate web-based information. Additionally, feedback by the teacher/facilitator was given frequently to the students during lectures and mostly during practical sessions. The final grade of the course was shaped by the contribution of the following a written exam, the literature review essay (group essay), presentation of the literature review in the online classroom, participation in classroom activities, reflection documents.

3.2.2.1.5.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

Supporting this attempt was the professors' willingness to go a step further than the ease of the written exam assessment and the relative freedom they have to decide their assessment methods. In order for this to continue they will have to be further supported by their organizations. We believe that it should become mandatory to assess student competences and knowledge through a diversity of methods, since students are diverse in their learning styles.

3.2.2.1.5.2 Hindering forces and how to deal with them

The major hindering force here was the time and energy needed to assess students in percentages. It takes a good amount of organizational skills to do so.

It may need further research into technological aids for this and of course teacher training. It may also be worth considering to get help from student placements in order to assist professors in such organizational loads, since time restraints are evident in their daily routines.

3.2.2.1.6 From lecturer to learning facilitator

In action learning students are given the opportunity to be in charge of their own learning. However, the teacher is the one responsible to create a learning environment that allows action learning to flourish and then take the role of the facilitator.

The facilitator, apart from the final exams, must have the opportunity to check the students' learning and progress throughout the course and offer several checkpoints for students to understand where they are, what they have learnt and if they are doing something incorrectly. Then students must be given time to practice and further develop their skills. Additionally, the facilitator should challenge the students' skills by providing them with appropriate feedback and relevant resources. Furthermore, feedback should be given frequently to the students.

Both modules consisted of lectures, classroom activities in which the professor acted as facilitator.

3.2.2.1.6.1 Supporting forces and how to build on them

Throughout these modules, the professors made great effort to accommodate the needs of the shift from lecture to action-based learning. This shift was marked by the effort of the professors to promote student competences as well as student knowledge. Based on our experience from the previous cycle activities, we decided to dedicate half a session at the beginning of the module to talking about the NEXTFOOD Project objectives, sustainable development and the core competences that promote sustainable development. As we noticed before, the Greek educational system and student learning expectations were based solely on content knowledge acquisition and the concept of skills and competences is alien to this learning culture. So, we framed the learning outcomes of the modules in a way that incorporated the core competences as well as a variety of other important learning skills such as information seeking skills, essay writing skills, presentation skills, group working skills, critical thinking, systemic thinking and problem-solving skills.

3.2.2.1.6.2 Hindering forces and how to deal with them

The acquisition of such skills and competences requires that the professor allows for time, resources and mental freedom for students to develop independently and it requires a facilitating role by him/her. However, in an on-line environment this is an extra challenge due to time-management and student management issues. From the reflection documents and the focus groups, we believe that the circumstances hindered this effort but at the same time, students in these modules mention a significant difference between these and other “mainstream” modules they attended in terms of richness in the learning environment, engagement, motivation and overall satisfaction.

So, dealing with this challenge would mean making good use of student feedback and promoting good examples.

3.2.2.2 What such change requires from teachers, students and institutions

From our experience and from the student and professor reports, we see that motivation, willingness and opportunities for alternative teaching methodologies are the most important factors on achieving the desirable shifts.

In the previous cycles professors often referred to financial shortages as a major challenge for action-based learning. However, as the pandemic has taught us during this cycle, action learning and multi-actor involvement is feasible without any time or financial burden made on the institution. Having said that, institutions have to give further incentive and training opportunities to professors to develop their teaching methodologies to deal with the challenges of the future. They need to incorporate teaching methodology in their educational culture and mindset and make it a mainstream theme of discussion and teacher assessment.

Students on their part would have to become more involved and engaged in their studies. From their part they should demand for an education that properly prepares them for their future professions.

4. Concluding remarks on the case development since previous reporting

4.1.1 Most useful and inspiring experiences (supporting forces)

There are numerous supporting forces as we have observed in the classes and as we have seen in our focus groups, reflection logs and based on our experience with student workshops. These are based on the very high motivational level of the actors we have worked with so far. There seems to be a great need from the part of students to participate in multi-actor, action-based activities and they are very receptive to ideas concerning sustainability. It seems that it is increasingly becoming a part of everyday social narratives and thus, younger generations may be more sensitive to and accepting of innovative ideas that support it. Professors on the other hand, are dealing with a great deal of professional stressors like time limitation, budget limitations, organizational hazards. However, action-learning seems to improve their relationship with their students and this allows for greater job satisfaction. Finally, professional actors and organizations have shown to have a high level of interest in connecting with Universities in order to fill skill gaps in their fields and to interconnect with the other parts of the system (political as well as academic).

4.1.2 Main obstacles/challenges encountered (hindering forces)

The hindering forces for change towards the NEXTFOOD approach that we continuously come across in our work is the lack of competence related culture within the universities, a general lack of a concrete conceptual framework for sustainability and the lack of experience with action-learning. These are issues that we have tackled directly with the professors and students that we have been working with. However, we are very aware that we are working with a very small number of people within a very large educational system.

Hindering forces on a higher level, as we have seen during numerous workshops and focus groups that we have carried out during this and previous working cycles, are the general lack of connection between academia and other actors in society who would be able to inform and update curricula and offer opportunities for experiential learning.

4.1.3 Lessons learned from the inspiring experiences and from dealing with the challenges

The lessons that we learned is that it takes time and perseverance in order to make a permanent change in culture. Although it is very common and easy to talk about action learning among professors and actors, it also takes concrete guidance and skill building on the part of the professors and the students to make it a reality.

We have also learned that this support can be given with relative ease now that we have established a good relationship with the institution. At the moment we can utilize a vast amount of tools and experiences in order to continue and disseminate our work to other professors and more students.

Building on the supporting forces would involve maintaining high motivation in the actors involved in the NEXTFOOD Project. This can be achieved in a variety of ways. First, during the next cycle of activities we need to retain wide connections with IHU by means of student workshops and seminars, that will enhance their learning experiences and their connection to activities that take place beyond their curriculums and academic environment. We will aim to involve IHU professors as much as possible, thus also enhancing the connection, trust and communication between them and the students.

We also aim to build on our previous workshops with the agricultural Network of Northern Greece and invite them to an open discussion with IHU officials in order to follow up with their intentions to connect and contribute to the university curricula.

4.1.4 Plans on how to move forward

In order to best serve the objectives of the NEXTFOOD PROJECT, the next activity cycle will need be more concentrated on studying the core competences in relation to real-life working conditions and the dynamics of multi-actor relationships. Thus, we are planning on supporting professors in designing their teaching modules as needed and concentrating our efforts on improving and implementing the learning set methodology with a smaller number of students.

So, our aim for the next cycle is to manage to enhance the action-learning culture we have started with the small number of professors we have been working with and to expand the benefits we have been seeing to the larger possible population. We plan on doing this by organizing a higher number of workshops and seminars that will enhance and create more permanent ties between students, professional organizations and the University.

We also plan to implement a GOAL SETTING TOOL, as an action-learning activity that may maintain and enhance the motivational levels that we have observed in student populations in IHU. This tool will be offered to the whole student population of IHU.

During the next cycle we also aim to give more support and promote the use of the precision Technology infrastructures that have been installed in IHU.

We are still dealing with the challenges of the pandemic so our plans remain flexible as to the method of implementation. However, the lessons we have learned from this cycle and also the technological readiness of students and professionals allow us to be optimistic as to the implementation of the next cycle activities.

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